

ABSTRACT

Student teaching is one of the essential requirements for education students to obtain a college degree in teaching. It is also the most challenging part of the curricular program. Failure to properly equip student teachers with the necessary skills in actual teaching means a teaching-learning disaster in the classroom. Obtaining information from student teachers who underwent a series of pedagogical strategies to equip them to become good teachers would give us insights into what should be implemented in training student teachers. Thus, this study was conducted with 26 BEED graduating students to determine the assessment levels of a classroom teacher's preparedness, capability, and acquisition of quality attributes as influenced by the strategies and methods employed by the program before engaging in actual classroom teaching. The results indicated that rigid pre-demonstration teachings and constructive comments, reading assignments, an English-speaking regime, and a series of seminar workshops, orientation sessions, and counseling are best practices in preparing student teachers to become effective classroom teachers and acquire appropriate values in the teaching profession.

Keywords: *Pre-Service Teachers' Training Program, State University, Competent Student Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Pre-Service Teachers' Training Program (PTTP) is the crux of any educational institution offering teachers' education curricular programs (Freeman et al., 2023). All the concepts, methodologies, practices, and theories of educational pedagogies imparted to the students during their first three years in college are organized into a methodological and practical form to equip student teachers to teach in actual classroom situations (Mangope et al., 2018). PTTP must be able to anticipate the real situations in the classrooms and community where student teachers would be teaching during their student teaching activity so that such students could be trained to effectively respond to such real classroom and community situations. PTTP activities must be systematically organized to provide student teachers with the abilities/competencies needed in the actual teaching situations. Failure to provide such competencies to student teachers means teaching disaster in classroom teaching situations. Therefore, PTTP should be reviewed, assessed, and improved from time to time to remain responsive to the changing environment in the classroom. Thus, maintaining, if not bettering, its approach, schemes, strategies, methodologies, and activities for a more responsive pre-service teachers' training program (Barnes et al., 2018).

Gathering data that could be used as a basis in decision-making for improvement and also whether to continue or stop an educational program is needed. One potential means of assessing the quality and effectiveness of a Program's input-output process is to examine its product (Bendermacher et al., 2017). A quality product means a quality production process. The quality and the degree of performance, competencies, desirable attitudes, and personal qualities acquired by clients through an educational program are indicators of the effectiveness of such a Program in attaining its goals and objectives. Gauging, therefore, the level of performance, teaching competencies, desirable attitudes, and personal qualities acquired by the pre-service education students from the Pre-Service Teachers' Training Program of the Western Philippines University – Quezon Campus is one of the meaningful assessment tools in determining if such training program achieved its goals and objectives. Sets of information that could be collected in the study would provide the Campus basis for improving its pre-service teachers' training program. Thus, this research was conducted.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This descriptive study was conducted with all of the 26 graduating Bachelor of Elementary Education of students of the Western Philippines University-Quezon Campus in the First and Second Semesters, SY 2017-2018.

Respondents. The respondents of this study are 26 graduating Bachelor of Elementary Education students enrolled in the Pre-Service Teachers' Training Program of the Western Philippines University - Quezon Campus.

Data Collection Procedure. Survey Questionnaire was the research instrument employed in the collection of data. Likert-type survey questions were observed in the construction of the research instrument. Rating scales were indicated.

Data Analysis Procedure. This study utilized weighted mean, frequency count, and percentage to statistically analyze and treat the data. The applicable statistical measure was also used for clarity of data presentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic and Economic Profile of the Respondents

Most of the respondents are in the age bracket 21 -30. The youngest is 19, and the oldest is 33. As to the sex of the respondents, 8 out of 10 are females; and only five of them were married.

Table 1. Age, sex, civil status, and number of siblings in the family

Criteria	Frequency (n=26)	Percentage
Age		
❖ 20 and Below	6	23.08
❖ 21 -30	7	26.92
❖ 31 and Above	2	7.69
❖ Not indicated	11	42.31
Sex		
❖ Male	5	19.23
❖ Female	21	80.77
Civil status		
❖ Single	21	80.77
❖ Married	5	19.23
Number of siblings in the family (in bracket)		
❖ Four and Below	9	34.62
❖ 5 - 7	13	50
❖ Eight and Above	4	15.38
Lowest: 2		
Highest: 9		

Religious Affiliation. Four and three out of 10 respondents are Roman Catholic and Baptist members as to religious affiliation, respectively. The rest are affiliated with other Christian denominations and Islam.

Table 2. Religious affiliation

Religious Affiliation	Frequency	Percentage
Roman Catholic	11	42.31
Baptist	9	34.62
Iglesia Ni Cristo	2	7.69
Apostolic Church of Christ	1	3.85
Islam	1	3.85
Aglipay	1	3.85
Christian Fellowship Church	1	3.85
Total	26	100.00

Occupation of Parents. As to parents' occupations, about seven out of 10 indicated that their mothers are housekeepers and few are teachers. Of their fathers' occupations, on the other hand, of 26, 10 are farmers, laborers, carpenters, and others.

Table 3. Occupation of parents of the respondents

Occupation	Father		Mother		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Housekeeper	0	0.0	18	69.23	18	34.62
Farmer	10	38.46	0	0.0	10	19.23
(Not indicated)	4	15.38	4	15.38	8	15.38
Teacher	0	0	3	11.54	3	5.77
(Deceased)	3	11.54	0	0.0	3	5.77
Laborer	2	7.69	0	0.0	2	3.85
Carpenter	2	7.69	0	0.0	2	3.85
Fisherman	1	3.85	0	0.0	1	1.92
Driver	1	3.85	0	0.0	1	1.92
Construction worker	1	3.85	0	0.0	1	1.92
Church's Minister	1	3.85	0	0.0	1	1.92
Fish vendor	0	0.0	1	3.85	1	1.92
(No occupation)	1	3.85	0	0.0	1	1.92
Total	26	100	26	100	52	99.99

Monthly Income of the Household. As to the estimated monthly income of the family, six out of 10 respondents are members of a household with a monthly income of Php 5,000 to Php 10,000, and three out of 10 have a monthly income between Php 5,000.00 and Below.

Table 4. Average monthly income of the respondents' family

Income (in Php)	Frequency	Percentage
5, 000.00 and Below	9	34.62
5, 100.00 to 10, 000.00	16	61.54
10, 100.00 to 15, 000.00	0	0.00
15, 100.00 and Above 20, 000.00	1	3.85
Total	26	100

The Choice of Pursuing the BEED Program

Choice of the Course. Out of the total respondents, only two signified that BEED as a degree program is their third choice. On the other hand, 12 out of 26 reported that the BEED program is their first and second choice, respectively.

Table 5. Choice of the course

Choices	Frequency	Percentage
First Choice	12	46.15
Second Choice	12	46.15
Third Choice	2	7.69
Total	26	99.99

Financial Support for Studies. As to how their studies in BEED Program were financially supported, 7 out of 10 respondents reported that scholarship grants and their family income supported them. Interestingly, four out of 26 respondents support their studies by self-financing them as working students.

Table 6. Sources in financing studies

Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
Scholarship Grants and family income	19	73.08
Self-financed/Working Student	4	15.38
Government Aide/Financial Aide	2	7.69
Support from family/family members/ relatives	1	3.85
Total	26	100

Reasons for Pursuing BEED. Table 11 indicates the five most salient reasons the respondents chose BEED as their degree program. These are the following: they loved to teach pupils, teaching can improve self-confidence, felt that they were fit in the teaching profession, could get a job quickly, and were inspired by their former teachers. Others reported that their parents influenced them to enroll in a teaching program, the availability of scholarship opportunities, and be respected in the community as future teachers.

Table 7. Reasons for pursuing in BEED Program

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
Love for pupils/kids	26	100
Improve self-confidence	25	96.15
BEED graduates can easily get a job	24	92.31
Influenced and inspired by a former teacher	22	84.62
Students' ultimate dream	21	80.77
Parents' influence and desire	20	76.92
Due to scholarship opportunities	20	76.92
To get respected in the community	20	76.92
Due to parents' expectation	18	62.23
To be able to meet professional people	14	53.85
The only affordable course	11	42.31
Persuaded by friends	10	38.46
Siblings are teachers	5	19.23

N=26

Student Teaching Program

Views on Student Teaching. Most said that student teaching is the most challenging load in the program. However, all of them reported that the course could equip them to become effective teachers and as an avenue for them to showcase their talent and potential, hone their professional growth and help develop their leadership skills.

On the other hand, most of the challenging views aired by the respondent regarding student teaching courses are that it requires too much effort and time. Other noteworthy challenging views are that it needs patience and understanding, creativity and artistry, and good communication skills.

Table 8. Views on practice teaching

Criteria	Frequency (n = 26)	Percentage
Positive Views		
❖ It provides an excellent opportunity to showcase one's talent and potential	26	100
❖ Equips student teachers to become effective teachers someday	26	100
❖ Influences professional growth of the student teachers	23	88.46
❖ Helps develop student teachers' leadership skill	20	76.92
❖ Makes student teachers feel satisfied	9	34.62
Challenging Views		
❖ It requires too much effort and time	26	100
❖ It needs patience and understanding	25	96.15
❖ Requires creativity and artistry	25	96.15
❖ Requires good communication skills (verbal and written)	23	
❖ Is the most challenging part of the BEED Course	20	76.92
❖ Expensive/requires money	16	61.54
❖ Requires pre-training inside the Campus	16	61.54
❖ It should be at least six months to 12 months	4	15.38
❖ Is just a burden	1	3.85

Level of Readiness of Student Teachers. To assess the status of readiness among the student teachers to go into actual teaching activities after they underwent the Pre-Service Teachers' Training

Program (PTTP), a rating continuum from 1 to 10 (10 being the highest rating) was used. Of the 26 respondents, only 4 rated their readiness to go in actual teaching activities at 7 and 6 (Table 9). More than 50 percent confidently rated their readiness at 8, and 4 rated ten as their readiness. This result implies they felt appropriately equipped, making them confident to engage in teaching activities. This readiness status among them signifies that they have received the training they should receive.

Table 9. Readiness status in undergoing practice teaching

Rating Scale*	Frequency	Percentage
10	4	15.38
9	4	15.38
8	14	53.85
7	2	7.69
6	2	7.69
Total	26	99.99

*10 = Very much Ready.... 1 = Not Ready

Factors of the Student Teaching Course Contributing Readiness. To determine what made them claim highly confident to undergo their actual student teaching activity, they were asked to supply attributes for each of the five given categories of the mechanisms employed by the program in training student teachers. After supplying the attributes they felt best described what they had acquired from each category, they were asked to rate them accordingly. These five categories are Pre-Demonstration Teaching, Required Library Works and Reading Tasks, Comments and Suggestions during Pre-Demo and Seminar-Workshops, English-Speaking Requirements, and Orientation and Seminar-Workshops (Table 10). A rating continuum from 5 – 1 (5 being the highest) was employed in assessing the respondents' level of readiness on the different attributing factors which were considered contributory to the level of readiness of the student teachers in handling actual classroom classes and activities at the Department of Education (DepEd).

Pre-demonstration Teaching. Rigid pre-demonstration teaching, which runs for 20 weeks with three sets of demonstration exposures, significantly affects the level of readiness of the student teachers to engage in actual classroom teaching activities. The respondents indicated that pre-demonstration experience helped them develop a commitment to given tasks, equip them for actual teaching engagement, make them confident to speak before a class, equip them in preparing good lesson plans, develop their ability to prepare visual materials and in using ITs, time management and among others. In fact, across respondents, 17 and 8 out of 26 respondents indicated "Very Much" and "Much" ratings, respectively, that rigid pre-demonstration indeed contributed to their readiness to face student teaching activities.

Library Works and Reading Tasks. On the other hand, library tasks developed the respondents' comprehension skills, improved vocabulary, loved reading, and could write grammatically correct sentences.

Comments and Suggestions during Pre-Demo and Seminar Workshops. Frank and honest comments of the members of evaluators, who are members of the education faculty, had a significant effect on the student teachers as these improved their teaching methodologies and strategies; and helped them develop open-mindedness.

English-Speaking Requirement. Moreover, speaking English requirement inside the campus vicinities enhanced their communication skills and confidence in expressing their ideas.

Orientation and Seminar-Workshops. Orientation and structured seminar-workshops, on the other hand, not only improved their teaching strategies and on what to do and not-to-do inside the classrooms but as well as opened their hearts to embracing and loving the teaching profession; and, across respondents, 22 out of 26 indicated that such orientation and seminar-workshops contributed a lot to their readiness to tackle the student teaching job.

Across all categories (and each of their attributes) and respondents, 7 out of 10 (73 percent) of them reported that these training mechanisms are *very much* instrumental in their readiness to do actual classroom teaching in the Department of Education (DepEd).

Table 10. Training mechanisms and their status in contributing to readiness in undergoing practice teaching

Training Mechanisms and Their Attributes	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding
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	5	4	3	2	1
Pre-Demonstration Teaching					
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped me to develop a commitment to my tasks	21	4	1	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings prepared me for my actual teaching	20	5	1	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings made me confident to talk in front	19	7	0	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings equipped me to prepare a (well-prepared) lesson plan	18	8	0	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped me improve my visual materials preparation capability/development	18	6	2	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped me become obedient	18	7	1	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped me develop my resourcefulness	18	7	1	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped me improve my time-management skill	17	8	1	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings helped them improve my IT/ET utilization	14	10	2	0	0
❖ Pre-demonstration teachings equipped them to perform well despite all odds	11	13	2	0	0
Mean	17.4	7.5	1.1	0	0
Library Works and Reading Tasks					
❖ Library Reading Activities helped me improve my comprehension skill	19	6	1	0	0
❖ Library Reading Activities helped me increase my vocabulary	17	9	0	0	0
❖ Library Reading activities let me appreciate reading/develop a love of reading	17	7	2	0	0
❖ Library Reading Activity helped me improve in writing grammatically correct sentences	11	14	1	0	0
Mean	16.0	9.0	1.0	0	0
Comments and Suggestions During Pre-Demo and Seminar-Workshops					
❖ Comments and Suggestions for improvement after demonstration teachings helped me acquire new teaching methodologies	23	3	0	0	0
❖ Comments and Suggestions for improvement after demonstration teachings helped me learn new strategies and ideas	22	3	1	0	0
❖ Comments and Suggestions for improvement after demonstration teachings taught me to become open-minded	22	4	0	0	0
Mean	17.0	3.3	0.3	0	0
English-Speaking Requirement					
❖ English Speaking requirement helped me in enhancing my communication skills	20	5	1	0	0
❖ English Speaking requirement developed my confidence in expressing ideas	14	12	0	0	0
Mean	17.0	8.5	0.5	0	0
Orientation and Seminar-Workshops					
❖ Seminar-workshop opened my heart about my profession	23	3	0	0	0
❖ Seminar-workshop equipped me with the knowledge on do's and don'ts inside the classroom	23	3	0	0	0
❖ Seminar-workshop contributed a lot to my emotional and mental preparedness	22	2	2	0	0

❖ Seminar-workshop equipped me to become more knowledgeable on the teaching strategies	19	6	1	0	0
❖ Orientation Program increased my level of awareness about student teaching	22	4	0	0	0
Mean	21.8	3.6	0.6	0	0
Total	448	156	20	0	0
Mean	19	6	0.8	0	0
Percentage	73.1	23.1	3.1	0	0

*Legend: 5 – Very much 4 – Much 3 – Slightly 2 – A little 1 – Not at All

Views and Attitude toward Teaching Profession

This section discusses the respondents' views and perceptions toward being a teacher, teaching as a profession, and cooperating teachers. Held views toward a specific concept, thing, or object influence individuals' attitudes. A positive view of a concept may influence a person to embrace the philosophy espoused by such a concept. An optimistic view on being a teacher, the teaching profession, and cooperating teachers would influence their minds to accept, adopt and embrace the reality of teaching and the love of the teaching profession.

Views or Attitudes toward Being a Teacher. Views or perception on something matters. Positive views or attitudes motivate individuals to do more and push forward on their tasks. Negative views or attitudes, on the other hand, stifle creativity and motivation to do better. This is because views and attitudes are deeply rooted in our belief system. Beliefs and feelings are some of the factors influencing attitude. Thus, positive views on being a teacher will influence an individual to embrace and love the teaching profession and be able to live and act on such held views.

To assess their views regarding the good attributes a teacher should possess, they were asked to indicate them and rate them according to the degree of importance. These held views regarding ideal traits a teacher should possess may be a carry-over concept from previous courses and pre-service training activities they underwent. Table 11 indicates 25 views of the respondents on what traits a teacher should possess. These were rated as 5 (Very Much Needed), 4 (Much Needed), 3 (Needed), 2 (Slightly Needed), and 1 (Not Needed). They consider these attributes essential for an excellent teacher to possess and live by. Notable is respect for cultural diversities, focusing on moral and correct values in teaching courses, flexibility, always speaking the truth, resourcefulness, understanding, welcoming challenges, and acting as a role model. Across respondents, 8 out of 10 rated the 25 attributes "Very Much Needed" for an individual to develop and possess to become a good teacher and mentor.

Table 11. Views on being a teacher

Descriptors	Rating Scale & Number of Responding (n=25)*				
	5	4	3	2	1
Teacher:					
❖ Respects cultural diversities	25	0	0	0	0
❖ Focuses on morality and values with subject knowledge	23	2	0	0	0
❖ Flexible	23	2	0	0	0
❖ Always speak the truth	23	2	0	0	0
❖ Resourceful	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Understanding	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Accepts/Welcomes professional challenges	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Role model	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Good learners	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Self-disciplined	21	4	0	0	0
❖ He considers students and himself as a finite human being	21	3	1	0	0
❖ Works with others to accomplish goals	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Develops students as whole	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Challenges the students	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Enabler	20	5	0	0	0
❖ Possesses a positive mental attitude	20	5	0	0	0
❖ Has the ability to know the student's strengths	19	6	0	0	0

❖ and weaknesses					
❖ Encourager (encourages learning)	19	5	1	0	0
❖ Inculcates discipline as a habit/nature	19	6	0	0	0
❖ Has the ability to transform and extend knowledge of her subject	19	6	0	0	0
❖ Looks into each student's individual needs	19	6	0	0	0
❖ Self-motivated	18	6	1	0	0
❖ Ignites/Motivates students to develop a passion for knowledge, innovation, and creativity	18	7	0	0	0
❖ Stretches the capability of the students	18	7	0	0	0
❖ Displays enthusiasm	16	7	2	0	0
Total	513	105	5	0	0
Mean	20.5	4.2	0.4	0	0
Percentage	82.0	16.8	1.5	0	0

Views on Teaching Profession. Table 11 shows their views on what traits a good teacher should possess. Table 12, on the other hand, indicates their views on teaching as a profession. In the same vein, positive views on teaching would benefit their desire to venture into teaching as a lifetime profession. Across respondents, 17 out of 25 indicated that teaching is a well-respected, prestigious (high-status), and noble profession. However, 17 also said it takes work to land a teaching job. This is because before one can land and hold a permanent teaching job, one has yet to hurdle the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Nevertheless, all of them wanted to pursue a teaching career.

As to negative views regarding teaching as a profession, a negligible number of respondents indicated that the teaching profession could not develop creativity, is a tedious job, and cannot positively impact life. Moreover, 11 indicated that teaching could not provide wholesome work satisfaction. This observation could be attributed to the observations they were exposed to during their student teaching exercise, where teachers are busy planning lessons and preparing myriad school-related activities.

Table 12. Views on teaching as a profession

Descriptors	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding** (n=25)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Positive Views					
❖ The teaching profession is well respected	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Teaching is an enjoyable profession	22	3	0	0	0
❖ Teaching is a respected profession like Medicine and Law	22	2	0	1	0
❖ It opens the door to learning	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Teaching is interesting	21	4	0	0	0
❖ Teaching is a noble profession	20	5	0	0	0
❖ In the teaching profession, one can interact with many people	16	8	1	0	0
❖ Teaching is a highly esteemed (prestige) profession	16	8	1	0	0
❖ Immediate family love teaching profession	12	10	2	1	0
❖ Peers consider teaching to be a promising career	11	13	1	0	0
❖ In teaching, one can easily land a job	1	3	0	4	17
Mean	16.7	5.7	0.4	0.5	1.5
Negative Views					
❖ The teaching profession can only provide some work satisfaction	11	8	2	2	2
❖ Teaching would not provide impact the life of teachers	0	2	0	3	20
❖ Teachers are boring people	0	0	2	2	21
❖ I don't want the teaching profession as it will not develop creativity	0	1	0	1	23

Mean	2.8	2.8	1.0	2.0	16.5
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*5 – Strongly Agree 4 – Agree 3 – Somewhat Agree 4 – Slightly Disagree 1 - Disagree

**One respondent did not provide ratings

Views toward the Cooperating Teacher. Table 13 shows the views of the respondents regarding their cooperating teachers. Fifteen criteria (descriptors) were provided for them to rate. These criteria were categorized into two. The first category is about the main things a Cooperating Teacher could do for the student teachers, and the second is about what Cooperating Teachers should do to help such student teachers hone their skills. Among all respondents, 18 out of 24 strongly agreed that Cooperating Teachers should check their lesson plans and assist them in their undertakings during the student teaching period. Besides, Cooperating Teachers are also expected to help student teachers solve classroom issues occasionally, e.g., absentee pupils and others.

Moreover, across all respondents, 16 out of 24 strongly agreed concerning what a cooperating teacher should do to hone student teachers' skills, such as modeling techniques in effective teaching, classroom management, lesson planning, assessment strategies, and the like.

Based on this finding, where all of them agreed (69, 29, and 2 percent strongly agree, agree, and somewhat agree, respectively) that the respondents are expecting from their cooperating teachers assistance throughout the student teaching period not only in the form of modeling them how to effectively teach and manage classroom but as well as to hone their skills as future professional teachers.

Table 13. Views on cooperating teachers and their responsibility as mentors

Descriptors	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding** (n=24)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Cooperating Teachers					
❖ Checks the student teacher’s prepared lesson Plan	23	0	1	0	0
❖ Assist the student teacher with her/his undertakings During her practice/student teaching	16	8	0	0	0
❖ Helps the student-teachers in solving arising issues in the classroom, e.g., absentee pupils, etc.	15	9	0	0	0
Mean	18	5.7	0.3	0.0	0.0
Assist the student teachers in honing their skills through:					
❖ Model effective teaching techniques	20	4	0	0	0
❖ Classroom management	19	5	0	0	0
❖ Preparation of instructional materials	19	5	0	0	0
❖ Lesson planning	18	4	2	0	0
❖ Observe, coach, and evaluate student teacher’s output	18	6	0	0	0
❖ Assessment strategies	17	6	1	0	0
❖ Allows student teachers to teach independently and collaboratively	15	8	1	0	0
❖ Keep records of evaluation and observations of the performances of the student teacher	15	9	0	0	0
❖ Let student teachers experience to collaborate with others through co-curricular activities/community activities	14	9	1	0	0
❖ Questioning techniques	13	11	0	0	0
❖ Conduct class observation and post conference	13	10	1	0	0
❖ Development and preparation of DepED forms	12	11	1	0	0
Mean	16.1	7.3	0.6	0.0	0.0
Grand Total	247	105	8	0	0
Grand Mean	16.5	7.0	0.5	0.0	0.0
Percentage	68.8	29.2	2.1	0.0	0.0

*5 – Strongly Agree 4 – Agree 3 – Somewhat Agree 4 – Slightly Disagree 1 - Disagree

** Two respondents did not provide ratings

Level of Performance in Doing Teaching and Related Tasks

Level of Performance of Required Tasks at Pilot Schools. The student teachers are expected to observe and perform necessary protocols and required tasks while doing their student teaching program at their pilot schools. These required tasks had been made clear to them during their pre-service training.

Table 14 presents 14 protocols and required tasks for these student teachers. In assessing their performance on these 14 protocols, a rating scale of 1 – 5 was used (of which five is the highest). Of these 14 said protocols, almost all of the respondents complied and obeyed. This means that their level of performance regarding these required tasks is about 100 percent. This high level of performance in complying, satisfying, and obeying the given duties and responsibilities could be due to the training programs and other pre-teaching activities they went through before sending them out to their respective pilot schools (see Table 11).

They showed very high respect to all teachers and personnel in their pilot schools, obeyed their cooperating teachers and other school authorities, returned all borrowed teaching materials prior to the end of the student-teaching program, came to class every reporting day, notified cooperating teachers and other concerned parties when cannot report to class and showing respect to the rights and privileges of the learners they were handling.

They also performed highly in preparing detailed lessons plan, observing the proper code of ethics as teachers, helping improve the classroom, accomplishing the required internship portfolio, and participating actively in all school-related activities.

Nobody rated their level of performance in all of the 14 protocols 3 (75%) or below. In fact, among all respondents, 8 out of 10 claimed that their performance level hit the 100% mark of doing and following all the required duties and responsibilities as student teachers.

Table 14. Level of performance of the required tasks while in their schools of assignments

Duties and Responsibilities	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding				
	5	4	3	2	1
1. Show respect to all teachers and personnel in the pilot school	25	1	0	0	0
2. Obeying the cooperating teacher and other school authorities	24	2	0	0	0
3. Returning all borrowed books and other teaching materials after completing the student teaching program	24	2	0	0	0
4. Coming to class every day in pilot schools	23	3	0	0	0
5. Notifying the supervisor, cooperating teacher, and other concerned parties when not reporting to class	23	3	0	0	0
6. Showing respect for the dignity and rights of the learners	21	5	0	0	0
7. Preparing and presenting detailed lesson plans for every actual teaching activity	20	6	0	0	0
8. Accomplishing the required internship portfolio	20	6	0	0	0
9. Observing the Code of Ethics, proper dress code, and punctuality in all activities during student teaching	20	6	0	0	0
10. Helping in the improvement of the classroom	20	6	0	0	0
11. Participating actively in all school-related activities	19	7	0	0	0
12. Being open to constructive criticism	18	8	0	0	0
13. Coming to class prepared all the time	17	9	0	0	0
14. Preparing instructional materials for use in every actual teaching activity.	17	9	0	0	0
Total	291	71	0	0	0
Grand Mean	21	5	0	0	0
Percentage	80.8	19.2	0.0	0.0	0.0

*Legend: 5 – 100% performance in following and obeying

- 4 – 85% performance in following and obeying
 3 – 75% performance in following and obeying
 2 – 65% performance in following and obeying
 1 – 50% following and obeying

Acquired Desirable Personal Qualities

Actual classroom teaching is the crux of learning all the theories, practices, and methodologies about teaching during the pre-service training. It is where all the pre-service training activities would be practiced in the real sense of the word in actual classrooms with real students/pupils coming from different sectors of society. Applying all the learned theories and practices during the pre-service teaching activities in the actual teaching environment would put the student teachers in the situation to discover and acquire more workable art and skills in teaching based on the principles they previously learned vis-à-vis the natural teaching-learning environment. Such a situation would force them to reflect on what must and should be acquired and learned more. Thus, based on such insights, they come to develop their own personal qualities.

As to this study, the respondents were asked to list down desirable qualities they acquired during the student teaching period. This gave them time to reflect on what desirable personal qualities they had acquired during the actual teaching experience vis-à-vis the theories and methodologies taught them while doing their courses and pre-service training. In the case of the respondents, Table 15 shows eight personal qualities they acquired as student teachers. Some noteworthy qualities they acquired are a sense of service, willingness to learn new learnings, sympathy, rapport with peers and supervisors, and tackling subject matter fast.

Table 15. Status of acquired desirable personal qualities

Acquired Personality Traits	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding (n=25)				
	5	4	3	2	1
I know I can give my best. I have a sense of service.	18	6	0	1	0
I am willing to learn, eager to grow, innovative, creative, and resourceful.	17	7	1	0	0
I am sympathetic and patient.	16	7	2	0	0
I am full of life, enthusiastic, energetic, and alive.	8	14	3	0	0
I am good at building rapport with teachers, students, and administration.	5	14	4	1	1
I am ready and equipped with multi-sensory aids, theories, and varied new updated methodologies.	5	16	4	0	0
I am confident.	0	11	6	4	4
I always tackle the subject matter fast.	0	10	6	5	4
Total	69	85	29	11	9
Mean	8.6	10.6	3.6	1.4	1.1
Percentage	34.4	42.4	14.4	5.6	4.4

*5 – Very much me 4 – It's like me 3 – Somewhat like me
 2- Slightly not like me 1 – Not like me

Perceived Weaknesses. Aside from desirable personal qualities they have acquired from the student teaching experience, they could also discern that they still need to learn and develop more desirable qualities to become a better teacher. Though only a few of them had expressed inadequacies in their teaching abilities, some expressed some personal weaknesses in terms of teaching abilities (Table 16).

Based on the pre-service teachers' training they had attended, coupled with the first-hand teaching experience in the Department of Education (DepEd), some realized that they needed to develop and improve their ability to express and articulate their ideas well. They also need to develop a skill in approaching and understanding the general view of a topic in order to craft coherent and logical lessons. Some need help adjusting to the new teaching-learning environment in their assigned field and in lesson planning, syllabus making, and construction of behavioral objectives.

Table 16. Perceived weaknesses

Indicators	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding (n=25)				
	5	4	3	2	1
I cannot express myself. I got full of ideas but could not articulate them well	3	12	7	3	0
Need to have a more integrated view of the lesson to avoid fragmented lessons	1	10	9	2	3
I think I have difficulty in classroom management hence, my inability to discipline class	0	9	3	11	2
I have difficulty adjusting to the environment, situation	0	8	8	3	6
I know I lack skill in the art of questioning	0	7	6	7	5
Difficulty in lesson planning, syllabus making, and construction of lesson objectives	0	6	6	8	5
Lack of mastery in their field; poor in content; lack of mastery of subject matter	0	5	6	9	5
Total	4	57	45	43	26
Mean	0.6	8.1	6.4	6.1	3.7
Percentage	2.4	32.4	25.6	24.4	14.8

*5 – Very much agree 4 – Much agree 3 – Agree 2- Slightly Agree 1 – Disagree

Level of Awareness on Teaching Competencies

Level of Awareness on Teaching Competencies. Four competency indicators were put forward to determine if the respondents had acquired awareness of the desired teaching competencies: teacher competency, classroom and time management, professionalism, and personal attributes or personality traits. Rating scales are in a 1 – 5 continuum, five being the highest in awareness.

In the teacher competency category, 18 competencies are listed for assessment. These competencies include, among other things writing lesson plans and preparation of teaching aids. Across all respondents and competencies in this category, 14 and 9 out of 25 indicated they are "Very much aware" and "Much Aware" of these competencies, respectively. This is about 6 and 4 out of 10. Nobody reported being unaware of the listed competencies (Table 17). This implies that they had internalized such competencies and acted accordingly on them.

On classroom and time management, 14 and 9 out of 25 indicated "Very much aware" and "Much aware," respectively. While in professionalism in doing their job, higher observations are noted; 19 and 6 reported that they are "Very much aware" and "Much aware," too.

As to the personality attributes, which include competencies in demonstrating obedience, self-control, and discipline, demonstrating patience and empathy for others, resourcefulness, sense of humanity and, among other things, 16 and 8 out of 25 indicated that they are "Very much aware" and "Much aware" of these, respectively, all of them are aware of such competencies.

Across all respondents and categories of competencies, the respondents registered a very high awareness of such competencies as indicated by the 96 percent "Very much aware – aware" continuum (64 percent, "Very much aware" and 32 percent, "Aware").

Table 17. Teaching competencies and level of awareness

Indicators	Rating Scale* & Number of Responding				
	5	4	3	2	1
Teacher Competency Indicators					
1. Checking to determine if students are progressing toward stated objectives	22	3	0	0	0
2. Writing daily lesson plans designed to achieve the identified objectives	18	7	0	0	0

3. Use of signaled responses, questioning techniques – guided practice to involve all students	17	8	0	0	0
4. Relating subject topics to existing student experiences	17	7	1	0	0
5. Preparation of presentable teaching aids and visual materials	16	8	1	0	0
6. Communicating instructional objectives to students	16	8	1	0	0
7. Giving clearly stated directions related to the learning objectives	15	10	0	0	0
8. Demonstrating the desired skill	15	10	0	0	0
9. Teaching the objectives through a variety of methods	14	11	0	0	0
10. Requiring all students to practice newly learned skills under supervision	14	8	3	0	0
11. Showing how the current topic relates to those that have been taught or that will be taught.	13	11	1	0	0
15. Using grammatically correct oral and written communication	13	11	1	0	0
12. Changing instruction based on the results of monitoring	13	10	2	0	0
16. Maintaining a written record of student progress. Utilizes fairly administered grading patterns based on identified criteria	13	9	2	1	0
17. Utilizing material that facilitates learning and thinking of an alternative in case the stated material is not available	12	12	1	0	0
13. Summarizing and fitting into context what has been taught	11	10	3	1	0
18. Requiring students to demonstrate mastery of stated objectives	9	12	4	0	0
14. Requiring students to practice newly learned skills without the direct supervision of the teacher	5	13	6	1	0
Mean	14.1	9.3	1.4	0.2	0.0
Classroom and Time Management Indicators					
1. Observing time, especially during daily routine. Uses minimum class time for non-instructional routines, maximizing time on task	16	6	2	1	0
2. Establishing rapport with students and providing a pleasant, safe, and orderly climate conducive to learning	14	10	1	0	0
3. Planning for the delivery of the lesson relative to short-term and long-term objectives	13	10	2	0	0
4. Defining expected student behavior	12	11	2	0	0
Mean	14.0	9.2	2.0	0.2	0.0
Professionalism					
1. Respecting the rights of the students	24	1	0	0	0
2. Displaying respect to other school officials and staff	24	1	0	0	0
3. Attending classes regularly (Student teachers are expected to be in the building on the same days and hours as regular teachers. Absences are inexcusable except for illness, death in the family, or other severe circumstances.)	22	3	0	0	0
4. Demonstrating obedience at all times	21	4	0	0	0
5. Performing duties on time (reports)	18	6	1	0	0
6. Participating in school-related activities	18	7	0	0	0
7. Responding professionally to administrative requests and direction	17	7	1	0	0
8. Working effectively with colleagues	16	9	0	0	0
9. Exhibiting professional growth	16	8	1	0	0
10. Demonstrating progress in utilizing current educational technology and media	13	12	0	0	0

Mean	19.0	6.0	0.3	0.0	0.0
Personal Attributes/Personality Indicators					
1. Demonstrating obedience	21	4	0	0	0
2. Demonstrating self-control and discipline	19	6	0	0	0
3. Displaying an enthusiastic/positive approach	19	5	1	0	0
4. Demonstrating patience and empathy for others	19	5	1	0	0
5. Practicing resourceful	16	9	0	0	0
6. Using a sense of humor	15	9	1	0	0
7. Using sound judgment (displays common sense)	14	10	1	0	0
8. Meeting difficult situations effectively	12	11	2	0	0
Mean	17	7.4	0.8	0	0
Total	632	322	42	4	0
Mean	16	8	1.1	0.1	0.0
Percentage	64.0	32.0	4.4	0.4	0.0
#One respondent did provide a rating					

*Legend: 5 – Very much aware; 4 – Aware; 3 – Somewhat aware; 2- Slightly not aware; 1 – Not aware at all

CONCLUSION

Based on the aforementioned salient points in the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The present Pre-Service Teachers' Training Program system is workable and commendable. Its implementation could be continued with improvement needed and essential. However, it should not be overdone.
2. Based on the issues experienced by the respondents, there is a need to craft or design new schemes and strategies, and methodologies, in addition to the existing and present system of the program, so that said perceived issues could be addressed and not be repeated in the subsequent batches of student teachers.
3. Mechanisms that will improve the communication and artistic skills and abilities of the student teachers should as well be given importance, if not emphasis, in crafting new schemes on top of the existing system of the program.

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